

Madani: Jurnal Ilmiah Multidisiplin

Volume 1, Nomor 6, Juni 2023

E-ISSN: 2986-6340

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8175320>

Applying Realia for Teaching Writing Skill at First Grade Students of Papua Senior High School

Isnaini Eddy Saputro¹

¹Universitas Pendidikan Muhammadiyah Sorong, Jln. KH. Ahmad Dahlan

NO.1 Aimas, Sorong, West Papua

Email: Isnaini1291@gmail.com

Abstract

Realia is a kind of media that can be used by the teachers to increase students' skill in writing descriptive text for stimulating the students' idea. This research is aimed to increase the students' writing skill at Papua senior high school. The sample of this research is 20 students of first grade at SMA Negeri 3 Sorong. The researcher uses quantitative method of one group pre-test and post –test as pre-experimental design. To collect the data of applying realia for teaching writing, it is used writing test that divided into pre-test and post test. Those tests are aimed to evaluate the applying of realia for students who learning English in writing skill. The kind of writing test is showed by descriptive text and analysed by using the effectiveness of treatment score that determined by mean score of pre-test and post test. The finding shows that the researcher found students' difficulties in writing skill from the pre-test result. Their obstacles in writing skill covered organizing the words, vocabulary, and grammar. The researcher applied relia to drill the students how to describe the realia by following the steps of descriptive text. The researcher concluded the result of pre – test and post test have different score. It showed by the pre –test (T1) was 58.75 and post test (T2) 65.62. It means that the students' writing skill is better when they learn English by writing an descriptive text using realia.

Key Words: Realia, Teaching English, Writing Skill, Descriptive Text

INTRODUCTION

People use language in interaction orally and writtenly as symbol, or sign, or code to deliver the meaning for others. The meaningful communication will create the good message between the speaker and listener. It is same with communication writtenly. The language will be organized well to show the meaningful for the reader. Therefore, the people will understand the meaning of text. Crebert et al, (2011) stated that most of people use media to communicate like E-mail and message. Communication does not only happen orally or face to face but the skill to written communication is needed contemporarily.

Written communication teaches the people to share their idea and thought. It is important for students who learn to develop their mind. The students learn how to develop the language skill first coming from what the students read. Then, the students express their idea according what the information is gotten. They drill their self to develop their cognitive, literacy, and thinking through writing activities. To support writing activity, the students need the appropriate media because it will guide them to organize the words. Hanafiah and Suhana (2009) revealed that media is used in teaching process to help the students for learning, to improve students' learning achievement, and it is part of teaching

instrument. Saputro (2022) explained that the effectiveness of teaching and learning process focused on the teaching instrument that provided by the teacher. It will support the students in learning English that related to 21st century skills. By using media, the students build high motivation to learn thus the students feel self-confidence and excited in acquire the target language.

This research uses realia to develop students' writing skill through writing a descriptive text. The teacher asks the students to focus on realia for describing what they have looked. Realia will stimulate students to develop their thinking skill to express their idea and organize the words. The teacher and students can use realia in the classroom such as things in the classroom, part of body, and pictures. The students can get much information to write their idea following the steps of descriptive text. Sitepu (2021) affirmed that realia is an object that real and semi concrete provided to support learning language. The students can look, touch, and bring it to everywhere for helping them in learning language. The students will get beneficial in learning English using realia. The students will learn kinesthetically which they acquire new language by handling the object. The students get good learning environment because they can learn by explaining the object. The students feel excited and fun learning. The students have time to present in front of the class by reading the concept (Nurbaeti, 2012). Therefore, the research tries to use realia for teaching English by writing descriptive text for first grade students of Papua senior high school.

Writing is the activity to thinking and organizing the idea to be a sentence and paragraph. The aim of writing is to deliver a written communication that train the people to read while connect their idea for interpreting the meaning. Students who learning language must have writing skill to support the other skills of English such as listening, speaking and reading. By students have writing skill, the students can engage in language learning process behaviorally, cognitively, and emotionally (Siburian, 2013; Sharples 1988; Deporter and Heracki, 2000).

The students can engage by following the steps of writing process covering pre-writing, drafting, revising, editing, and publishing. Those process develop the students to change their behavior in getting ready to write. It is mentioned as pre-writing. The students can write a topic by focusing on the environment that they can use it as an object or we can say as drafting. Then, the students can write based on the environment and it needs to clarify with their friends about their idea. The students can work together to correct each other of their idea in a writing concept consisting of correction the content, form, grammar, style, and mechanics of language. Thus, the students can share or publish their written after the students had followed the stages of writing process (Tomkins, 1994; Harris, 1969).

To establish this research of writing skill, the researcher establishes the students to write descriptive text that stimulates the students for expressing their idea of people, places, and things. The students use descriptive text to prompt their writing skill by organizing their idea by describing the process, event, personality, place, and object. To describe all objects, the students must focus on the rhetorical structures of descriptive text such as identification and description part. Therefore, the students can guide and organize their written well (Siburian, 2013; Pardiyono, 2007).

METHOD AND DESIGN

This research uses quantitative research method and pre – experimental one group pre- test and post test design. The sample is only one class that consists of 20 students that learn by English writing skill by using realia. To collect the data, this research applies writing test that given in the first meeting and the end of meeting as the evaluation of

applying realia in teaching English of writing skill. The researcher determines the writing score by following the components of writing. The explanation includes in table below.

Table 1. Analytical of Writing Scoring Rubric (Weigle, 2002)

Components of Writing	Scores	Indicators
Content	4	- Relevant to the topic and easy to understand
	3	- Rather relevant to the topic and easy to understand
	2	- Relevant to the topic but is not quite easy to understand
	1	- Quite relevant to the topic but is not quite easy to understand
Or Organization	4	- Most of the sentences are related to the main idea
	3	- Some sentences are related to the main idea
	2	- Few sentences related to the main idea
	1	- The sentences are unrelated to each other
Vocabulary & Mechanic	4	- A few errors in choice of words, spelling, and punctuation
	3	- Some errors in choice of words, spelling, and punctuation
	2	- Occasional errors in choice of words, spelling, and punctuation
	1	- Frequent errors in choice of words, spelling and punctuation
Grammar	4	- A few grammatical inaccuracies
	3	- Some grammatical inaccuracies
	2	- Numerous grammatical inaccuracies
	1	- Frequent grammatical inaccuracies

The table above explains the writing scoring rubric which the researcher uses it to observe the progress of students' learning English in writing descriptive text. Moreover, the researcher will collect the scores of each items and analyze them by computing the individual score, mean score, percentage score, standar deviation and the effectiveness of treatment score that computed by pre – test score and post – test score.

FINDING AND DISCUSSION

The findings showed that the research had been conducted pre – test t collect the first data for knowing the students' ability of writing skill. After that, the researcher given treatment for six times with different topics thus the students can write six descriptive text and the researcher conducted post – test to evaluate the students' progression in learning English by writing descriptive text. The result of pre – test is most of students difficult to organize the idea in paragraph. Furthermore, another problem of the students in writing skill is the content, vocabulary and mechanic and grammar. Therefore, it can be showed by the students' pre –test score in table below.

Table 2. Tabulation of Students' Score in Pre-test

No.	Subject	Components of Writing				Scores
		Content	Organization	Vocabulary & Mechanic	Grammar	

1	VVS	4	4	3	3	14
2	AFIL	3	3	2	2	10
3	NLS	3	2	2	2	9
4	YS	3	3	3	2	11
5	NN	1	2	2	3	8
6	RRW	2	2	2	2	8
7	FHM	3	2	2	2	9
8	NHA	3	3	2	2	10
9	EKA	3	2	2	3	10
10	KAK	3	2	2	2	9
11	AC	2	2	2	2	8
12	GAT	2	2	2	3	9
13	MNT	3	2	2	2	9
14	IY	2	2	2	2	8
15	DS	2	2	2	3	9
16	ET	2	2	2	3	9
17	AMA	3	2	2	3	10
18	AAH	3	2	2	3	10
19	JMW	3	2	2	2	9
20	TT	1	2	3	2	8
Total						187

The table above explains the students' pre – test score. There are 20 students who have range of pre – test score around 8 until 14. The lowest score is 8 and the highest score is 14. The students' score are computed by the indicators of writing components such as content, organization, vocabulary and mechanic, and grammar. Hence, the total score of pre –test for 20 students overall is 187.

After the researcher gets the students' pre – test score, the researcher gives the treatment for 6 times by teaching the students how to write a descriptive text. Then, the researcher conducts the post – test for assessing students' learning achievement. The researcher gives writing test and the students' post –test score are revealed in table below.

Table 3. Tabulation of Students' Score in Post-test

No.	Subject	Components of Writing				Scores
		Content	Organization	Vocabulary & Mechanic	Grammar	
1	VVS	4	3	3	3	13
2	AFIL	4	3	3	3	13
3	NLS	3	2	2	3	10
4	YS	3	2	2	3	10
5	NN	3	2	2	2	9
6	RRW	3	2	2	3	10
7	FHM	3	3	2	2	10
8	NHA	3	3	2	3	11
9	EKA	3	2	2	3	10

10	KAK	3	3	2	2	10
11	AC	2	2	2	2	8
12	GAT	3	2	2	3	10
13	MNT	3	2	2	3	10
14	IY	3	2	2	3	10
15	DS	3	2	2	3	10
16	ET	2	2	2	2	8
17	AMA	4	3	3	3	13
18	AAH	4	3	3	3	13
19	JMW	3	3	3	2	11
20	TT	3	3	2	3	11
Total						210

The table above shows that the students' post – test score after giving treatment for 6 times. The students learn English by writing descriptive text for 6 topics. The researcher finds that after the students learn English by using realia, the students still get the lowest score same with pre – test score. The lowest score of post – test is 8 and the highest score is 13. Thus, the total score of post –test is highest than pre – test score. The total score of post –test is 210 for 20 students. Furthermore, the mean score of pre – test and post – test are different. The mean score of pre – test is 58.75 and the mean score of post – test is 65.62. Therefore. The researcher concludes that the mean score of pre-test (T1) is 58.75 while post-test (T2) was 65.62. It means that, the result of post-test (T2) is better than pre-test (T1). The total score of post test in table is higher than the scores obtained in pre-test.

Both result of pre – test and post test show that the students undergo progression when they learn English by using realia. The students feel interesting in learning English. They can express their idea in written communication well. Moreover, the students are concern to components of writing and the steps of descriptive text therefore those are as guidance for them. Realias has contributed in learning language process. It helps the students to write a descriptive text easily and accurately. By using realia the students do not waste much time, because they can deliver the words based on the object directly.

CONCLUSION

Based on the result of the research that had been done in pre experimental one pre-test and post-test design of the research, it can be the conclusions that there is an progression. The ability in writing descriptive text improves after taught by using realia (real object). The students can describe the object easily in descriptive text because the student see the object directly. The students are able to follow the teacher's instruction to write based on qualities, parts, and characteristics. It is showed by the students' score from pre-test and post-test. The pre-test shows the total score of the students' writing result 1175 , the mean was 58.75 or 10% students are in 'Very Good', 35% students are in 'Good' and 55% students are in 'Fairly'. While the result of post-test is 1312.5, the mean is 65.62 or 20% students are in 'Very good', 65% students are in 'Good' and 15% students are in 'Fairly'. It means that realia is as instructional teaching to help the students in writing skill for describing an object. The students can focus to describe easily and organize the idea for being the meaningful sentence.

References

- Crebert, G., Patrick, C. J., Cragolini, V., Smith, C., Worsfold, K., & Webb, F. (2011). Written communication toolkit. *Griffith Institute for Higher Education*.
- De Porter, B., & Hernacki, M. (2000). *Quantum learning*. PT Mizan Publika.
- Hanafiah, N., & Suhana, C. (2009). Konsep strategi pembelajaran. *Bandung: Refika Aditama*.
- Harris, D. P. (1969). *Testing English as a Second Language*.
- Nurbaeti, B. (2013). Teaching Vocabulary Using Realia Media at the Third Grade Students of SDN 1 Tegalmunjul–Purwakarta.
- Pardiyono. 2007. *Pasti Bisa! Teaching Genre Based Writing*. Yogyakarta: CV. Andi Offset
- Saputro, I. E. (2022). Students' Perception toward ICT In English Learning. *INTERACTION: Jurnal Pendidikan Bahasa*, 9(2), 552-559.
- Sharples, M. (2002). *How we write: Writing as creative design*. Routledge
- Siburian, T. A. (2013). Improving students achievement on writing descriptive text through think pair share. *IJLLALW*, 3(03), 30-43.
- Sitepu, S. B., & Kurniawati, L. A. (2021). An exploration on the use of realia-mediated instruction for teaching English for young learners. *Research and Innovation in Language Learning*, 4(1), 36-51.
- Tompkins, G. E. (1994). *Teaching writing: Balancing process and product*. Macmillan College.
- Weigle, S. C. (2002). *Assessing writing*. Cambridge University Press.